

Investigating Light Losses in LiquidO Detectors: Understanding the Effect of Adhesives on Optical Fibres

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Abstract

The effect on light transmission of adhesives applied to wavelength shifting fibres was investigated, as part of the LiquidO detector development program. LiquidO is a potentially revolutionary opaque scintillator detector technology that will be used for the ν CLOUD experiment detecting reactor neutrinos at the Chooz nuclear power station. LiquidO detectors use wavelength shifting fibres to transport the scintillation light to silicon photomultipliers for detection at the edges of the detector. The low trapping efficiency of wavelength-shifted light by the fibres is a significant source of light loss in the detectors. This project investigated a possible source of loss of the small fraction of light that is trapped by the fibres, by studying the effect of adhesives used on the fibres to hold them in position. A test method was developed using a pulsed LED mounted at the centre of a length of fibre and silicon photomultipliers at each end to detect the light.

Two adhesives were tested: a UV-curing bonding agent, and an epoxy, named Bondic®, and 5-minute Z-POXY, respectively. In one particular test, each adhesive was applied to cover 0.5 cm of a fibre's outer surface on one side of the LED's position. For Bondic®, a (10.7 ± 0.1) % light loss was found; for Z-POXY, a (1.7 ± 0.1) % light loss was found.

The effect of the refractive index of the material surrounding the fibre was investigated, as a possible explanation for the results and to determine if the light lost caused by the adhesives was likely to be collected in a LiquidO detector in any case. Immersing one side of the fibre in ultrapure water had no detectable effect on the light level, whereas mineral oil caused a loss of (4.7 ± 0.1) %. Importantly, applying Z-POXY to a fibre with a length immersed in oil caused no additional light loss compared to oil alone. The fibres in a LiquidO detector will likely be immersed in an opaque scintillator with a refractive index higher than that of the fibre's external cladding (as was the case with oil), therefore, the results suggest that the use of Z-POXY is unlikely to reduce the light yield of the detector. Areas for further research include modifications to the test setup and method to improve applicability and time efficiency, and improving the accuracy of fibre simulations to better understand the results and LiquidO detectors in general.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

This project contributed to the development program of LiquidO, an innovative opaque scintillator particle detector technology. In this chapter, the wider context of the project is provided. First, the concept of scintillation and its application in scintillator detectors are introduced, which have been used in many experiments, particularly in the field of neutrino physics. The concept of LiquidO is then described, and how it can overcome the limitations of traditional scintillator detectors is discussed, demonstrating its potential impact.

1.1 Scintillator Detectors

Scintillator detectors have a vast range of uses, including in particle physics experiments and medical imaging devices. These detectors consist of a scintillating material that emits light when a particle transfers energy to it. The emitted light is then collected by a light detector, such as a photomultiplier tube (PMT) or a silicon photomultiplier (SiPM), which converts the light to an electrical signal which can be stored and analysed. Scintillator detectors offer advantages such as sensitivity to energy and fast time response which have been exploited in a variety of experiments, particularly in the field of neutrino physics where they are used to detect the products of neutrino interactions in the detector material.

1.1.1 Scintillation

Scintillation is the process by which a scintillating material emits light after absorbing energy from incident radiation, which excites an atomic electron in the scintillator. Scintillators can be characterised as organic or inorganic scintillators. There are plastic scintillators which are a solution of organic scintillator in a solid, scintillator gases, and scintillator crystals. Organic scintillators, which are aromatic hydrocarbon compounds containing benzene-ring structures, that produce scintillation light through luminescence [1]. There are two types of luminescence that occur in organic scintillators: fluorescence and phosphorescence. Fluorescence is characterised by its rapid decay time (within 10^{-8} s of absorption) [1]. Phosphorescence has a delay between absorption and emission because the excited state is metastable. The length of this delay depends on the material. For example, BaF_2 has a fast decay time of 0.8 ns and a slow decay time of 300 ns.

Scintillators are used as particle detectors as they can provide a variety of information about incident particles due to their sensitivity to energy, fast time response, and pulse shape discrimination capabilities [1]. Above a certain threshold energy, the light output of a scintillator is near-linear with the absorbed energy. This means that the number of detected photons can be used to infer the energy of the interacting particle. In some cases, approximating the relationship between light output and deposited energy as linear is acceptable. However, for low-energy and/or heavier particles the non-linearity needs to be considered, for example using Birks' semi-

empirical model [1]. Light production via fluorescence happens rapidly, which allows precise timing information to be obtained. Additionally, the recovery time of scintillators can be fast, making the dead time short and high count rates possible. It can be possible to distinguish between different types of particles by analysing the shape of the emitted light pulses. Particles with different ionising power excite the scintillator through different fluorescence mechanisms, which result in different emitted light pulses. This is useful for particle identification. A scintillating material is a good candidate for a detector if it [1]:

1. Is highly efficient at converting the incident energy to fluorescent radiation.
2. Is transparent to the wavelengths of emitted fluorescent light.
3. Emits light at a wavelength compatible with the sensitivity of the light collector in the detector.
4. Has a short decay constant.

1.1.2 Scintillator Detectors and Experiments

To use scintillation for particle detection, the scintillator needs to be coupled with a light collector that will convert the light to an electrical signal that can be stored and analysed. Therefore, there are three main components to a scintillator detector: the scintillator, light guides, and light collectors. Light guides, such as optical fibres, are needed to transmit the scintillation light to the light collectors, such as PMTs or SiPMs.

Liquid scintillator detectors (LSDs) have formed numerous physics experiments that have made important discoveries and measurements, particularly with the advent of electronic light detection [2]. The field of neutrino physics has particularly utilised LSDs, starting from the first evidence of the existence of neutrinos by Cowan, Reines et al. in 1956 [3]. Due to their design, scintillator detectors require transparent scintillating material to enable light collection at the edges of the detector. This limits the detectors in two ways.

First, the transparency requirement limits the volume of the detector due to the attenuation length of light in the scintillator [4]. This parameter is defined as the length after which the light intensity is reduced to a factor e^{-1} of its initial value [1]. The further the light has to travel through the detector, the more likely it is to be absorbed. Therefore, too large a detector may not be able to detect enough light, particularly from particle interactions that occur far from the edges. This limitation is particularly significant in neutrino physics where interaction cross-sections are incredibly small, and so increasingly large detectors have been built to observe rare processes. The JUNO experiment detector contains 20 kilotons of liquid scintillator, pushing the limit of the possible size of a detector due to the transparency requirement [5].

Second, the need for transparency severely limits the type and concentration of dopants that can be added to the scintillator as they cause a loss of transparency [4]. The higher the concentration of dopants, the higher the loss of transparency. Adding other elements to the scintillator enhances the capability of the detector to search for rare processes. For example, the SNO+ experiment will search for neutrinoless double beta decay by doping the liquid scintillator with a 0.3% concentration of natural tellurium containing the ^{130}Te isotope, known to undergo two-neutrino double beta decay [6]. If the transparency requirement could be removed, scintillator detectors with higher concentrations of dopants could be used, which would enable further rare processes to be searched for more efficiently.

An alternative approach to improve position resolution is to segment the detector. This has worked well in detectors such as MINOS, which consisted of iron-scintillator planes containing $1\text{ cm} \times 4.1\text{ cm}$ width scintillator strips with an embedded optical fibre per strip for dual-end light collection. However, detector segmentation presents many challenges. For instance, complex and costly engineering is required to design and build segmented detectors. The segmentation itself results in *dead material* due to the use of non-scintillator materials, and the spatial resolution is limited by the size of the segments. Finer segmentation results in more dead material, higher costs, and increased surface area of the scintillator exposed to potential contaminants. The

latter has implications for the rate of background events in the detector; radioactive purity of the detector is crucial to minimise background. Achieving this purity is challenging with solid scintillator detectors. In contrast, liquid detectors, such as the SNO+ detector [7], can undergo purification processes. The Tokai to Kamioka (T2K) near detector upgrade to the Super Fine-Grained Detector (SuperFGD) has pushed the boundaries of segmentation. The SuperFGD design uses approximately two million 1 cm^3 cubes of plastic scintillator, read out along three orthogonal directions by optical fibres. This enormous engineering project will provide nearly 4π coverage for neutrino interactions at the T2K near detector, lower energy thresholds, and reduce systematic uncertainties in measuring neutrino oscillation parameters [8]. However, continuing this approach in detector development has limitations. For example, doubling the position resolution of the SuperFGD would require eight times as many cubes.

Nuclear power stations produce a high flux of neutrinos, making them a convenient source for neutrino experiments. The Double Chooz experiment used antineutrinos produced by the reactors at the Chooz-B nuclear power station to study antineutrino disappearance and aimed to measure, or set an upper limit, on the θ_{13} mixing angle. The Double Chooz detectors had a spatial resolution of 15.3 cm, which had implications for signal event selection. To detect electron antineutrinos, the experiment used their interaction with protons in the detector material:

$$\bar{\nu}_e + p \rightarrow e^+ + n. \quad (1.1)$$

The subsequent annihilation of the positron with an electron in the detector material produced two gammas that could be detected. However, the spatial resolution of the Double Chooz detectors was not sufficient to resolve the many scintillation light balls produced by the gammas. In contrast, a beta particle from a background event produces a single light ball in the detector, which would be indistinguishable from the interaction that produced two gammas. As a result, background events would be incorrectly selected as signal events. Consequently, the experiment's use of spatial reconstruction of events for particle identification was limited but instead relied on event energies for signal selection. Due to this limited background rejection capability, the detectors were constructed underground to shield them from background radiation, adding to engineering work and cost.

To continue progress with neutrino experiments, there is a need for a new scintillator detector technology that can overcome the limitations of current detectors, which are constrained by the requirements of transparency and segmentation, and have limited imaging capability for particle identification.

1.2 LiquidO

LiquidO is a new detector technology that has the potential to overcome some of the limitations of scintillator detectors, detailed in Section 1.1.2. LiquidO uses an opaque scintillator with a short scattering length, confining the light to the point of production. The short scattering length, $\mathcal{O}(\text{mm})$, causes a scintillation photon to undergo a random walk about its origin [4]. This results in a sphere of light produced around the particle interaction point. The absorption length of the scintillator is intermediate-long, allowing photons to undergo many short scatters without being absorbed.

To extract the light, a lattice of wavelength shifting (WLS) fibres is immersed in the scintillator. When a photon's random walk intersects a fibre, the light can enter it and be transmitted to a silicon photomultiplier (SiPM) light detector at the end of the fibre. By using SiPMs at both ends of the fibres, the position of the particle interaction can be determined from the time difference between the signals at each end [4].

LiquidO detectors use components which have been extensively researched and used in previous successful scintillator detectors. The innovative application of these well-established technologies in the LiquidO technique makes it a promising new approach to particle detection. A

prototype LiquidO detector built and used at the University of Sussex, with the components labelled, is shown in Fig. 1.1. This prototype has fibres in one direction only, but future prototypes will have fibres in two orthogonal directions.

Figure 1.1: Prototype LiquidO Detector with labeled components.

The development of LiquidO aims to overcome some of the limitations of transparent scintillator detectors and push the boundaries of neutrino experiments. A significant advantage is its ability to achieve a far higher signal-to-background ratio through high-resolution imaging, which enables the rejection of background and improved selection of signal events. Unlike previous experiments using transparent scintillator detectors, e.g. Double Chooz as detailed in Section 1.1.2, a LiquidO detector can differentiate between beta and gamma events based on their reconstructed topology.

LiquidO detectors offer the unique feature of self-segmentation, by confining scintillation light to the point of production before its collection. The spatial reconstruction of events in LiquidO detectors is made possible by recording the location of the fibre that collected light, and the time difference between light collection at each end of the fibre. For example, the individual scatters of gammas in the detector can be resolved, which was not previously achievable with detectors such as those used for Double Chooz. The imaging capability of LiquidO is illustrated in Fig. 1.2, showing a simulation of light hitting each fibre in a 1-cm pitch lattice in two scenarios: an opaque scintillator with a 5 mm scattering length (left) and a transparent scintillator (right) [4]. Despite identical fibre configurations and light collection, the resulting images differ greatly in the information they provide about the event, in this case, a positron with 1 MeV of kinetic energy. The confinement of light around each energy deposition with the opaque scintillator preserves the spatial information of the event, allowing the formation of a high-resolution image.

Figure 1.2: Imaging capability of opaque (left) and transparent (right) scintillators [4].

This technology enables particle detectors to be constructed with excellent position resolution more easily than the segmented detectors described in Section 1.1.2, and without dead material from segmentation. However, building a LiquidO detector presents its own set of engineering challenges, such as filling the detector containing a large number of delicate fibres with liquid scintillator, and routing the fibres to the SiPMs.

The ν CLOUD experiment will use a five-tonne LiquidO detector to study reactor neutrinos at the Chooz power station. Compared to other reactor neutrino experiments which require detectors to be built underground for shielding against background radiation, the LiquidO detector will be stationed on the surface, making it easier and more cost-effective to construct. However, without the shielding from rock, the detector will be subject to a high background rate. The success of the experiment in selecting signal events will depend on the high-resolution imaging capability that enables excellent particle identification from the spatial reconstruction of events to distinguish between electrons, positrons, and gammas. A purer selection of neutrino interaction events will ultimately result in a more accurate and precise measurement of the reactor neutrino flux, with this experiment.

As opacity is desired for a LiquidO detector, there is more potential for doping the scintillator compared to transparent LSDs. As discussed in Section 1.1.2, this makes a LiquidO detector an excellent candidate to search for rare processes in specific isotopes. Additionally, LiquidO can potentially use known scintillators with high light output that have previously been rejected for use in detectors due to their poor transparency [4]. The opaque scintillator currently used in LiquidO prototype detectors is called NoWaSH, an acronym of ‘Novel Waxy Scintillator Heidelberg’. NoWaSH has a linear alkylbenzene (LAB) organic scintillator base, with a diphenyloxazole (PPO) wavelength shifter, and paraffin wax which adds opacity [9].

1.3 Context and Objectives of this Project

This project was part of the ongoing development of LiquidO detectors, with a focus on maximising the light yield of the detectors. The main source of light loss between the scintillator and light collection is the WLS fibre acceptance, where around 90% of the light re-emitted by the fibre can be lost.

To maximise the detector’s light yield, it is therefore important to minimise losses of the small amount of light that is trapped by the fibres, before it reaches the SiPMs. The detector’s energy resolution and sensitivity to low-energy and rare events, improve with a higher light yield. Adhesives used on the fibres during detector assembly have the potential to cause light to be lost from the fibres. However, the effect of materials in contact with the fibres on light transmission had not yet been investigated as part of the LiquidO detector development. Therefore, this project aimed to develop and utilise a method to test for light losses due to materials in contact with the fibres. The adhesives tested in this project were researched and selected by an engineer in the LiquidO group at the University of Sussex. Through this investigation, the project contributed to the ongoing effort to understand and improve the overall performance of LiquidO detectors.

Chapter 2

Hardware and Software

This chapter introduces the hardware and software used to test for light losses along optical fibres. Table. 2.1 lists the components along with links to relevant figures for images of them. Fig. 2.1 shows the test bench with the equipment labelled.

Table 2.1: List of components with abbreviations and links to relevant figures.

Component	Abbreviation	Figure
Hamamatsu S13360-1350PE Silicon Photomultipliers	SiPMs	2.5b
Light-emitting diode	LED	2.7b
LED pulser	Pulser	2.7a
LED pulser power supply	Pulser PSU	2.1
Saint-Gobain BCF91A wavelength shifting fibres	Fibres	1.1
Silicon Bread Board	SiBB	2.5a
Silicon Bread Board Power Supply	SiBB PSU	2.1
Silicon Connectors	SiCs	2.5b
WaveCatcher Digitiser	WaveCatcher	2.8

Figure 2.1: Test bench setup with labeled equipment.

2.1 Silicon Photomultipliers (SiPMs)

The function of a light sensor is to absorb incident light and convert it into an electrical signal which can be stored and analysed [10]. To measure light losses along optical fibres and to detect scintillation light in LiquidO detectors, $1.3 \times 1.3 \text{ mm}^2$ Hamamatsu S13360-1350PE SiPMs are used. SiPMs are solid-state semiconductor detectors that have properties that make them well-suited for light detection. Compared to other light detectors such as photomultiplier tubes (PMTs), SiPMs are small, cheap, and operate at lower bias voltages. SiPMs offer high gain, photon detection efficiency, and timing resolution. They are capable of detecting down to a single photon, making them ideal for low light yield detectors and precision light loss measurements.

They are reverse-biased semiconductor detectors, meaning that a voltage is applied across the device in the opposite direction of its normal operation. SiPMs consist of a dense array of micro-cells (pixels). Each contains a Geiger-mode avalanche photodiode (APD) that detects single photons, connected in series with a quenching resistor that halts the avalanche [11]. A high reverse voltage is applied to the APD, resulting in a saturation output so that it produces a pulse of the same amplitude whenever it detects a photon. The electrical signals from all the pixels within the trigger window are summed, resulting in an output signal that is proportional to the number of photons detected [12]. The output signal produced by the SiPM in response to the incident photon is small and requires amplification before it can be digitised for storage and analysis [10].

2.1.1 Semiconductor Photodetectors

SiPMs are semiconductor detectors with silicon as the active material. The operation principle is that incoming radiation ionises atoms in the silicon forming electron-hole (e-h) pairs. An applied electric field separates the charge carriers and drifts them toward electrodes, where they induce a signal. The band gap energy between the valence and conduction band of the silicon is the minimum amount of energy required to create an e-h pair.

To enable photon detection, the electric field that drifts the created e-h pairs needs to be high. However, a high electric field can thermally induce a leakage current in the silicon. The silicon is doped to create a pn-junction. Atoms with one valence electron more than silicon are added to provide n-doping, and atoms with one less valence electron are added to provide p-doping. The p- and n-doped materials are brought together to form a pn-junction which causes charge separation through thermal diffusion to occur. At the pn-junction, a depletion region is formed, where there are no mobile charge carriers. This means that a pn-junction is capacitor-like, with the p- and n-regions serving as the electrodes and the depletion region as the charge-free space between them. With a reverse bias voltage applied, the depletion region grows with the applied electric field strength [10].

Fig. 2.2 shows the three operational modes, detailed below, of a photodiode depending on the reverse bias voltage [13].

Photodiode Operating Mode

When absorbed by the silicon, a sufficiently energetic photon can create an additional e-h pair by exciting an electron from the valence band to the conduction band through the photoelectric effect. The applied electric field drifts the created e-h pair to the electrodes. Photoelectrons form the current that is the signal in a semiconductor photodetector, which is proportional to the number of photons [13].

Avalanche Photodiode Operating Mode

APDs use avalanche charge multiplication as an internal gain mechanism. When a higher bias voltage is applied, the field at the pn-junction increases, enabling the primary electrons to gain

Figure 2.2: Operation modes of semiconductor photodetectors [13].

enough energy to generate secondary e-h pairs [13]. These secondary e-h pairs can further generate more secondary e-h pairs, leading to an avalanche effect. This results in an increase in the total amount of charge carriers per incident photon, a phenomenon known as impact ionisation [10]. The measured current is amplified and proportional to the number of detected photons. As only electrons create the secondary e-h pairs, the current only flows in one direction and so is self-quenched [13].

Geiger-Mode Avalanche Operating Mode

Further increasing the bias voltage takes it above the *breakdown voltage* in which both electrons and holes have enough energy to create secondary e-h pairs [14]. At this point, the electric field is high enough that a single primary charge carrier can trigger an avalanche, allowing for the detection of single photons in Geiger-mode APDs. The current increases very rapidly and so the rising edge can be used for high-precision timing of the photon arrival [13].

The avalanche is self-sustaining and so must be stopped using a quenching resistor, which causes the bias voltage to drop below the breakdown voltage [14]. The diode then needs to recharge before it can detect any more photons, which limits the maximum rate at which photons can be detected. This period of time is known as *dead-time*, and is characterised by the time constant of the circuit.

2.1.2 SiPM Characteristics

Breakdown Voltage

When the bias voltage applied to an SiPM exceeds its breakdown voltage, the avalanche photodiode operates in Geiger-mode (see Section 2.1.1). The difference between the bias voltage and the breakdown voltage is called the overvoltage. Determining the optimum overvoltage involves balancing different SiPM characteristics that can either enhance or compromise overall performance.

Gain

The gain of an SiPM is the number of charge carriers generated during the avalanche response to an absorbed photon. The gain increases linearly with the applied overvoltage, as shown in Fig. 2.3a [15], leading to a better signal-to-noise ratio and lower detection thresholds.

Photon Detection Efficiency

The photon detection efficiency (PDE) of an SiPM is the probability that the SiPM produces an output signal in response to an incident photon. PDE is calculated by the product of the

quantum efficiency, fill factor, and avalanche probability [12]. Of these, the avalanche probability has an overvoltage dependence which is shown in Fig. 2.3a [15]. Additionally, PDE is a function of the wavelength of the incident light, resulting in a peak sensitivity around a specific wavelength (see Fig. 2.10c in Section 2.6.1).

Noise

SiPMs have three sources of noise: dark pulses, afterpulsing, and crosstalk. Dark pulses are output signals produced by thermally-generated charge carriers. These pulses are indistinguishable in shape from photon-generated pulses and contribute to the background rate of photon detectors. The rate of dark pulses depends on temperature since they are produced by thermally-generated charge carriers. Therefore, the ambient temperature should be controlled to minimise the DCR and improve the photodetectors' signal-to-background ratio. The exponential temperature dependence of the DCR is shown in Fig. 2.3b. Afterpulsing is due to charge carriers

(a) Overvoltage dependence of the gain, crosstalk probability, and PDE [15].

(b) DCR as a function of temperature, at a constant gain [12].

Figure 2.3: Overvoltage and temperature dependence of Hamamatsu S13360 series SiPMs.

trapped in silicon defects during the avalanche multiplication that are released with a delay dur-

ing the recharge phase of the SiPM response. This results in an additional pulse on the tail of the original pulse. Crosstalk occurs when photons emitted during avalanche multiplication are reabsorbed in neighbouring microcells, causing additional signals. Afterpulsing and crosstalk probabilities increase more than linearly with overvoltage. The total DCR is the sum of the rates of dark pulses, afterpulsing and crosstalk pulses. Trigger methods, such as coincidence triggering or setting a higher threshold, can be used to reduce the background noise. The three different kinds of noise in SiPMs are represented in Fig. 2.4.

Figure 2.4: Representation of SiPM output signals for the different kinds of noise [16].

Determining the optimal overvoltage requires a trade-off between SiPM characteristics. Higher gain and PDE are desirable for high-sensitivity/low-light-level applications, but they also increase the DCR, necessitating triggering and event selection techniques.

2.2 SiCs and the SiBB

The custom SiC boards feature an SiPM at the centre and are connected to the SiBB which supplies high voltage (HV) to the SiPMs and monitors their temperatures. For the work in this project, the SiPM HV was set to 54.00 V. The SiBB with two SiCs connected can be seen in Fig. 2.5a which shows the inside of the dark box, and Fig. 2.5b is a close-up view of an SiC with an SiPM at the centre.

(a) Dark box interior with the SiBB and an SiC labeled.

(b) SiC with an SiPM at the centre.

Figure 2.5: The SiBB and an SiC.

SiBB Software

The SiBB software facilitates the control of the high voltage (HV) to the SiPMs and the monitoring of their temperatures. Fig. 2.6 shows a screenshot of the graphical user interface of the SiBB software.

Figure 2.6: SiBB software graphical user interface screenshot.

Under the ‘High Voltage Power’ header, the HV to the SiPMs can be precisely adjusted with a tolerance of 0.01 V by entering a value or using the dial and can be turned on and off with the toggle switch. After typing a value into the input box, press enter to apply the voltage.

The channel numbers in the software correspond to the numbered slots on the SiBB to which the SiCs connect. The input box below the ‘DACs’ header can be used to manually apply a bias voltage to individual, or all, SiPMs. This lowers the bias voltage on the selected SiPM channel and is used to normalise the gains of SiPMs with different breakdown voltages. For this project, two SiPMs with similar breakdown voltages were used making bias voltage offset unnecessary.

Settings can be saved into a configuration file by selecting ‘Save Setup’, and saved settings can be applied by selecting ‘Load Setup’ and choosing a configuration file. Utilise the overcurrent and output voltage control features by ticking the boxes. Note that these boxes are not ticked whenever a configuration file is loaded in, regardless of whether they were ticked or not when the settings were saved.

The ‘Measure HV’ feature is useful for checking the bias voltage of the SiBB is at the expected value. This feature can identify if there is a short circuit, which may be caused by an incorrectly connected SiC or a broken SiPM, which prevents the voltage from reaching the set value. The measured voltage should be checked after switching the HV off and before opening the lid of the dark box, as the SiPMs must not be exposed to high light levels when the bias voltage is above their breakdown voltage.

Set the reference temperature to the ambient temperature of the dark box, typically 22 °C. The bias voltage of each SiPM is adjusted based on its temperature relative to the reference temperature to offset the effect of temperature on the gain of SiPMs, as detailed in Section 2.1.2. The temperature of each SiPM can be monitored, and a live plot of temperature over time can be displayed. This is useful for knowing when the temperature has stabilised which is advisable before starting to take data.

2.3 LED Pulser

The LED pulser, shown in Fig. 2.7a, used as a light source in this project was designed and built at the University of Sussex. It was designed to provide a stable and adjustable light source for use with SiPMs and has a variable frequency ranging from 500 Hz to 100 kHz. The pulser can be connected to any standard LED via a cable, which allows for quick and easy test setup changes.

To power the pulser and adjust its output signal, an external power supply (PSU) is used. This allows for fine adjustments of the pulser signal, enabling the control of the LED light output down to the photon level. The pulser requires a voltage of 12.00 V.

For the tests in this project, an optical fibre was passed through the casing of an LED coupled to an SiPM at each end. This ensured a constant distance between the light source and the fibre. The LED light was contained to its casing by heat shrink and black epoxy, as can be seen in Fig. 2.7b. The pulser was used to flash the LED, producing a small amount of light that was transmitted along the fibre and detected by the SiPMs. The typical light level recorded at each end of the fibre in these tests was an average of seven photons, indicating the pulser's ability to deliver very small signals.

For this project, the pulser was operated at a frequency of 550 Hz. This allowed for efficient data acquisition with high statistics, while also ensuring that there was enough time between each signal to prevent any overlap of light from the previous flash in the fibre.

(a) Pulser used to illuminate the LED.

(b) Sealed LED connected to pulser.

Figure 2.7: LED pulser used as the light source.

2.4 WaveCatcher Digitiser

A 16-channel WaveCatcher digitiser was used to record the signals from the SiPMs. This digitiser consists of 12-bit 3.2 GS/s switched capacitor digitiser boards and modules, which use SAM-LONG analog memory chips [17]. Due to the high sampling rate, these digitisers are well-suited for very fast signals, such as those generated by fast scintillators coupled to SiPMs, making them valuable tools in the LiquidO detector development program.

To connect an SiC to a channel on the digitiser, an MCX cable is used. Additionally, the LED pulser described in Section 2.3 can be connected to the external trigger channel at the back of the WaveCatcher. This setup enables the pulser's signal to trigger the recording of the signal from the SiPMs at each end of a fibre. Fig. 2.8 [17] shows the front of the WaveCatcher, where the MCX cables from the SiCs are connected.

Figure 2.8: Front view of the 16-channel WaveCatcher digitiser [17].

2.4.1 WaveCatcher Software

The digitiser is controlled and the data is read out using the WaveCatcher64Ch software. This software provides an oscilloscope-like tool with a graphical user interface (GUI) that enables the use of the hardware functionalities. The key features utilised in this project were the waveform display and external trigger mode. All acquired data can be saved to files, either in ASCII or binary format, for offline analysis. Binary format is preferred as it limits file sizes and the time required to read in the data.

Main

A screenshot of the ‘Main’ tab in the WaveCatcher software is shown in Fig. 2.9a, with the external trigger and two SiPM channels selected for data acquisition. In this project, two channels were used to record data from the SiPMs at each end of a fibre. To enable or disable data acquisition for a channel, click the circle next to its channel number. The recording status of a channel is indicated by a coloured circle if recording is enabled, and a black circle if it’s not. The colour of the circle matches the signal trace on the waveform display as shown in Fig. 2.9b. The square wave signal from the pulser, used as the external trigger and to illuminate the LED, is shown as a white line and the SiPM signals are pink and blue lines. The external trigger signal was viewed on the display before taking data to check it was on and behaving as expected, but it was not recorded as it was not used in the analysis. Including the pulser’s signal in the data would have needlessly increased file sizes.

Switch the display to ‘Partial’ to limit the frequency at which events are displayed, to prevent saturation of the system which limits the sampling rate. Compare the event rate during data acquisition with the pulser rate of 500 Hz to monitor for saturation. If the event rate is lower than the pulser rate, increase the number in the ‘Partial: every ... events’ box. To record data, select the ‘Finite’ run type and then save the waveforms to file in the ‘Run’ tab in the navigation bar of the GUI before starting the run.

Trigger

A screenshot of the ‘Trigger’ tab in the WaveCatcher software shows the trigger configuration in Fig. 2.9c. Here the channel(s) to be used to trigger the recording window are selected. For this project, the trigger was on the rising edge of the LED pulser’s signal to record in a window when the LED was on.

(a) Main tab.

(b) Signal display.

(c) Trigger tab.

Figure 2.9: WaveCatcher software.

2.5 Data Analysis Software

To process and analyse the SiPM signals recorded by the WaveCatcher digitiser, offline software is used. The first step involves processing the data with ‘RecoMore’ which is an adaption by Joshua Porter, in the LiquidO group at the University of Sussex, of the ‘RecoZor’ software [18]. This software is designed to decompose the SiPM output waveforms into single-photoelectron (PE) pulses by identifying individual peaks in the signal, and fitting a template waveform to the signal by applying a horizontal shift and vertical stretch [19]. The output of RecoMore is a file that contains the event number, time of the event, and pulse amplitudes with their times since the trigger, for each recorded channel.

To further process the RecoMore output for use in this project, which only required the pulse sizes and channel information, I wrote a script called ‘EB_recoMoreScript.py’. This utilises functions from the Sussex LiquidO software repository to read the data and save the pulse sizes to a CSV file for each channel. This extra processing step saves time overall since it only needs to be performed once, and the faster-to-read CSV files are then available for use in the analysis code.

All code from this stage onward was written by me in Python, and access to the GitHub repository is available upon request (see the Preface for details). The functions used to analyse the data and generate the plots in this project are contained in the script titled ‘EB_fibreFunctions.py’. A script called ‘EB_fibreTestScript.py’ allows the user to input parameters specific to the data being analysed and calls the functions. This data analysis software was developed specifically for this project, and details of the analysis process can be found in Section 3.5, following the explanation of the test method.

2.6 Wavelength Shifting Fibres

Multiple wavelength shifting (WLS) optical fibres are formed into a lattice and immersed in the opaque scintillator in LiquidO detectors, as described in Section 1.2. The fibres serve to transport the light from the point of production in the scintillator to the edges of the detector for light collection at the SiPMs. To couple the fibres to the SiCs, standard FC connectors are attached with epoxy.

While previous LiquidO detector prototypes used Saint-Gobain BCF91A multi-clad fibre, future prototypes and detectors will use Kuraray B-3(200)SJ double-clad fibre. For the tests in this project, the Saint-Gobain fibres were used due to the limited availability of Kuraray fibres. However, the outer claddings of the two types of fibre have the same index of refraction, so it is

likely that the results are mostly generalisable to the Kuraray fibres.

Fibre Composition

Saint-Gobain BCF91A multi-clad fibres consist of a core, an inner cladding and an external cladding. The core material is a polystyrene-based material with a refractive index of 1.60. The core contains fluorescent dopants selected to produce the desired optical characteristics. For this project, fibres with a 1 mm diameter were used. The inner cladding is acrylic with a refractive index of 1.49 and a thickness of 3% of the fibre diameter. The external cladding is fluor-acrylic with a refractive index of 1.42 and a thickness of 1% of the fibre diameter. The additional layer of cladding means that these fibres trap significantly more light than single-clad fibres [20].

2.6.1 Absorption, Wavelength Shifting and Re-emission of Light

When light from the scintillator is absorbed in the fibre core, it is re-emitted isotropically in the core at a longer wavelength. This enables light that enters a fibre through its lateral surface to be transmitted along its length, as it can be emitted at angles above the critical angle for total internal reflection. Without this isotropic emission, the light would be refracted out of the fibre at the same angle it entered, preventing its transmission along the fibre (see Section 2.6.2 for more details). The wavelength shift also provides two further advantages: it matches the wavelength to the peak sensitivity of the SiPMs, and it prevents light that escapes the fibre from causing additional scintillation by shifting it further out of the scintillator’s absorption spectrum [21].

Wavelength shifting in fibres occurs through fluorescence, wherein the fibre core absorbs incident light and re-emits it at a longer wavelength. This process, called Stokes fluorescence, results in the emission of lower energy photons compared to the absorbed photons, as vibrational energy is lost to the surroundings before the emission [22]. The energy difference between the absorbed and emitted photons is known as the Stokes shift. Fibres with larger Stokes shifts are more efficient since they have less overlap between their absorption and emission spectra, reducing the likelihood of self-absorption [23].

To enable wavelength shifting, the fibre core is doped with a fluorescent dye which is selected based on the suitability of its absorption and emission spectra for the application. To maximise efficiency in LiquidO detectors, there are three wavelength-dependent elements that need to align: the scintillator, WLS fibres, and SiPMs. The emission spectrum of the scintillator needs to match the absorption spectrum of the WLS fibres, and the emission spectrum of the WLS fibres needs to match the peak sensitivity of the SiPMs (see Section 2.1.2). The NoWaSH scintillator (see Section 1.2) used in LiquidO detectors contains linear alkylbenzene (LAB) scintillator and a diphenyloxazole (PPO) wavelength shifter [4]. Fig. 2.10a shows the emission spectra of a NoWaSH sample with 80 wt.% LAB, 20 wt.% wax and a PPO concentration of 0.3 wt.% [9]. Fig. 2.10b [24] shows the absorption and emission spectra of Saint-Gobain BCF91A multi-clad WLS fibres, which are not optimally matched with the PPO emission spectrum. Instead, Kuraray B-3(200)SJ fibres which are a better match, will be used, as mentioned in Section 2.6. However, it can be seen in Fig. 2.10c [15] that the emission spectrum of the fibres is very well matched to the peak sensitivity of the SiPMs. A liquid scintillator comprised of LAB and PPO is used in the SNO+ experiment. The SNO+ collaboration measured and reported the absorption spectrum of their scintillator, which can be seen in Fig. 2.10d [7]. These spectra show that there is negligible absorption of light in the emission spectrum of the fibres. Therefore it is highly unlikely for light that escapes from the fibres to cause the NoWaSH to scintillate, which would lower the accuracy of position and timing measurements from the detector.

(a) Scintillator emission spectrum for a NoWaSH sample [9].

(b) Absorption and emission spectra of Saint-Gobain BCF91A multi-clad WLS fibres [24].

(c) Photon detection efficiency of Hamamatsu SiPMs [15].

(d) Absorption spectra of LAB with and without PPO wavelength shifter [7].

Figure 2.10: Optical properties of LiquidO detector components.

2.6.2 First Approximation: Basic Principles of Reflection and Refraction

While the behaviour of light in an optical fibre is complex, it is useful to start with a simplified model that considers the basic principles of reflection and refraction. This model provides a foundation for understanding how light is transmitted from its production point in the scintillator to an SiPM at the end of the fibre. It also explains the mechanism by which light is lost from the fibre due to the refractive index of the surrounding material.

Fig. 2.10a shows that the peak of the emission spectrum of NoWaSH is at 360 nm. Given this wavelength, a 1 mm fibre diameter fibre corresponds to approximately 2778 wavelengths of the incident light in a LiquidO detector. Therefore, for the purposes of studying the behaviour at the fibre surfaces, the cylindrical surface of the fibre can be approximated as flat [25]. The refractive index of a material is defined by the ratio of the speed of light in a vacuum to the speed of light in that material [26]. The refraction of light travelling from a medium with an index of refraction n_1 into a medium with an index of refraction n_2 , is shown in Fig. 2.11 [26]. There are three cases: $n_2 = n_1$, $n_2 > n_1$ and $n_2 < n_1$.

In the case of a LiquidO detector, the light is first travelling from the opaque scintillator that produced it to the external cladding of the WLS fibre. In this case $n_2 < n_1$, so the light is

Figure 2.11: Partial reflection and refraction of light travelling from a medium with an index of refraction n_1 into a medium with an index of refraction n_2 [26].

Figure 2.12: Total internal reflection of light above the critical angle of incidence [26].

bent away from the normal. If the light is not absorbed by the fibre on its path across the core, the light then encounters the inner cladding, where $n_2 > n_1$, and is bent toward the normal. The light then reaches the boundary with the core of the fibre where, again, $n_2 > n_1$, so the light undergoes further refraction toward the normal. Finally, light that was not absorbed in the core is refracted out of the fibre into the scintillator at the initial angle of incidence.

On the other hand, if scintillation light is absorbed by the fluorescent dopant on its path across the fibre, it will be wavelength shifted and re-emitted isotropically within the core. This light has the chance to be trapped by the fibre and transmitted along it. If the angle of incidence, at the core-inner cladding boundary, of the re-emitted light is greater than the critical angle, it will be totally internally reflected along the fibre. The critical angle, θ_c , for total internal reflection to occur at the boundary of two media is given by

$$\theta_c = \arcsin \frac{n_2}{n_1} \quad (2.1)$$

where n_1 is the initial medium refractive index, and n_2 is the second medium refractive index [26]. Fig. 2.12 [26] shows an example of total internal reflection occurring at a glass-air boundary for incident angles greater than the critical angle, and refraction occurring for incident angles less than the critical angle. This trapped light will repeatedly undergo total internal reflection, travelling down the core of the fibre and can be detected by an SiPM at the end. Light re-emitted with an angle less than the critical angle of the core-inner cladding is not trapped and will be refracted out of the core and into the inner cladding. This light is either totally

internally reflected down the inner cladding or refracted into the external cladding. Light that enters the external cladding is either refracted out of the fibre into the scintillator or travels down the external cladding through total internal reflection. The addition of the fluorine component to the external cladding reduces the refractive index of the material, which enables total internal reflection at the boundary between the inner and outer cladding [27]. Light that travels down the claddings can also reach the end of the fibre for collection. However, this is less likely for external cladding light which has a short attenuation length (see Section 2.6.4). The losses of external cladding light occur mainly at the cladding-scintillator boundary which is susceptible to degradation from exposure to the environment, including abrasion and accumulation of impurities [21]. Fig. 2.13 is a diagram showing the three components of the light in fibres [28].

Figure 2.13: Drawing of a double-clad fibre with the three components of light [28].

2.6.3 Light Acceptance and Trapping Efficiency

The ability of a fibre to capture and transmit wavelength-shifted photons to the end of the fibre is called light acceptance, and the trapping efficiency of the fibre represents the amount of light trapped in the fibre relative to the amount of wavelength-shifted light [20]. Trapping efficiency is an important parameter for determining the light yield of a detector.

Light propagation in optical fibres can be described by axial rays, meridional rays, and skew rays. Axial rays travel directly along the axis of the fibre, while meridional rays pass through the fibre axis after each reflection [29]. Skew rays do not pass through the fibre axis after each reflection but instead follow a helical path around the fibre axis [30]. Skew rays are depicted in Fig. 2.14 to aid in picturing their path in three dimensions [30].

Figure 2.14: Drawing of a double-clad fibre showing a skew ray of light [30].

The model described in Section 2.6.2 provides the meridional approximation for light acceptance in a fibre, where light with an incident angle greater than the critical angle, θ_c , will be trapped and undergo total internal reflection to reach the end of the fibre [20]. The trapping

efficiency in the meridional approximation for forward propagating photons is [20]

$$\epsilon_m^{1/2} = \frac{1}{2} (1 - \cos \theta_c) \quad (2.2)$$

where the 1/2 superscript highlights that this is the trapping efficiency for forward propagating light, which is half the total light when the backward propagating light is also considered. Both the forward and backward components are relevant for a LiquidO detector and for the work in this project as light is collected at both ends of the fibres. By considering the skew rays, trapped light rays with incident angles less than the critical angle are also accounted for. The skew rays contribute

$$\epsilon_s^{1/2} = \frac{1}{2} (1 - \cos \theta_c) \cos \theta_c \quad (2.3)$$

to the trapping efficiency [20]. Together, the total trapping efficiency is

$$\epsilon^{1/2} = \epsilon_m^{1/2} + \epsilon_s^{1/2} = \frac{1}{2} (1 - \cos^2 \theta_c), \quad (2.4)$$

which is approximately twice the trapping efficiency in the meridional approximation [20].

The trapping efficiency depends on the core-cladding interface's symmetry, and any deviation from it, such as diameter or ellipticity variation, causes refraction of some skew rays. Since skew rays undergo more reflections, and therefore have a longer optical path length, they are attenuated faster. Consequently, longer fibres have a trapping efficiency closer to $\epsilon_m^{1/2}$ than $\epsilon^{1/2}$ [20].

The minimum permitted skew angle, γ , at a given axial angle, θ , is determined by the critical angle condition [20], which states

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{\sin \theta_c}{\sin \theta}. \quad (2.5)$$

A photon is more likely to be trapped when it is emitted closer to the cladding than when it is emitted near the centre of the fibre; the range of azimuthal angles for which light is trapped increases with the distance from the centre of the fibre. With the origin at the centre of the fibre and unity at the core-cladding boundary, the meridional approximation accurately estimates the trapping efficiency when photons are emitted from radial positions < 0.8 . Fig. 2.15 is a result of

Figure 2.15: Trapping efficiency of photons as a function of emitted radial position [20].

fibre simulations by Achenbach and Cobb showing the trapping efficiency as a function of radial position [20]. They also found that for curved fibres, as is the case in this project, photons on

near meridional paths are refracted out of the fibre most. Achenbach and Cobb’s simulation considers only the core component of light in the fibre, which is justified for long fibres as the cladding components will be lost due to their shorter attenuation lengths. However, for optical path lengths < 1 m, as in the case of this project, the cladding light components can contribute significantly to the transmitted light.

To deepen our understanding and interpretation of the results obtained in this project, a simulation was developed by Dr Sogo Bezerra, in the LiquidO research group at the University of Sussex, to investigate the trapping efficiency of fibres surrounded by media with different refractive indices [31]. The methodology of the simulation was as follows:

1. Define the optical properties of the WLS fibres: the refractive indices of the core, inner cladding, and external cladding materials.
2. Define an initial surrounding medium of air with a refractive index of 1.00.
3. Calculate the critical angle for total internal reflection at each interface by Equation 2.1.
4. Calculate the angle of refraction at each interface using Snell’s Law.
5. Calculate the trapping efficiency for each component of the light by Equation 2.4.
6. Repeat for a range of surrounding medium refractive indices up to the refractive index of the external cladding.
7. Plot the cumulative trapping efficiency of the core, inner cladding, and external cladding components of the light as a function of the surrounding medium refractive index.

The dependence of the trapping efficiency of the fibre on the refractive index of the surrounding medium is shown in Fig. 2.16, using the results of the simulation. When the surrounding

Figure 2.16: Trapping efficiency of each component of the light as a function of the surrounding material refractive index [31].

medium’s refractive index matches that of the fibre’s external cladding, the trapping efficiency is reduced by a factor of three compared to when the fibre is surrounded by air. This has implications for the light yield of LiquidO detectors, in which the fibres are immersed in a medium with a higher refractive index than their external cladding. Note that the simulation assumes a perfect fibre, which does not contain bends, defects or impurities that reduce the trapping efficiency, particularly of the external cladding light. Therefore, the trapping efficiency of fibres used in the tests of this project, and LiquidO detectors, is likely to decrease faster than the linear relationship predicted by this simulation.

2.6.4 Attenuation Length

The attenuation of light travelling through a fibre is typically modelled as an exponential decay, with the attenuation length defined as the distance over which the light intensity reduces to e^{-1} . There are two primary sources of attenuation in fibres: absorption and scattering. As mentioned in Section 2.6.3, skew light experiences greater attenuation from absorption and scattering losses caused by irregularities at the core-cladding interface. This is because it undergoes more reflections and therefore has a longer optical path length than meridional light as it propagates through a fibre [21]. The self-absorption of the wavelength-shifted light in the fibre occurs due to overlapping absorption and emission spectra of the fluorescent dyes in the core [21]. Rayleigh scattering of light occurs at inhomogeneities in the fibre material such as defects and impurities [30]. The external cladding is far more susceptible to such inhomogeneities due to its exposure to the environment. Surface defects on the external cladding such as dust, dirt, and abrasions, cause attenuation of the external cladding component of the light. As a result, the external cladding light has a shorter attenuation length than the other light components. For this reason, the attenuation length can be modelled as the sum of two exponentials, for the short and long attenuation lengths. The expected order of the long component is 4 m, while the short component is expected to be around 30 – 50 cm [32].

Chapter 3

Development of the Test Method

The aim of the work in this chapter was to find the dependent variable to be used as the measure of the light level in optical fibres, enabling the detection of light losses. The stability of this variable was assessed and the systematic uncertainty of measurements of light losses this introduced was quantified. This systematic uncertainty was used to find the limiting factor in the precision of measurements possible with this test setup and method. The various test designs used in this project are detailed in Section 3.3. In addition, Section 3.4 details validity tests of the proposed test procedure that were conducted, which improved our confidence in attributing the cause of an effect to the test parameter. The developed test method, and analysis process, of the measurements of light loss with this setup are detailed in Section 3.5.

3.1 Default Test Setup and Method

The following setup is the default test setup and method, any deviations from this will be noted in the specific test sections. A length, typically 130 cm, of Saint-Gobain BCF91A multi-clad fibre with a mounted LED is connected at each end to a $1.3 \times 1.3 \text{ mm}^2$ Hamamatsu S13360-1350PE Silicon Photomultiplier (SiPM). The lid of the dark box and optical cloth shield the SiPMs from ambient light. The equipment (HV to SiPMs, WaveCatcher digitiser, pulser and LED) is shown in Fig. 3.1 are then switched on and left for the system to stabilise. See Chapter 2 for details of the equipment used. The SiBB software, detailed in Section 2.2, is used to control the bias voltages of the SiPMs and monitor their temperatures with a precision of 0.05°C . While the stabilisation time of the LED pulser is not known, experience suggests waiting for at least one hour after switching it on. Runs are taken with the trigger for an event as the signal from the pulser which causes the LED to flash. For every event, the signal from the SiPMs at each fibre end is recorded, regardless of whether light is detected or not. Test runs of 8,000 events are taken to assess the light level from the LED pulser, as detected by the SiPMs at each end of the fibre. As the light level varies depending on the fibre position of the LED, due to attenuation, and there is some instability over time of the pulser, a particular voltage one day is not guaranteed to produce the same light level another day. Therefore, it is important to take a short test run, process the data, and look at the light level before proceeding with a test. Once the desired light level is achieved, runs are taken for the initial condition measurement.

To implement the test condition, the lid of the dark box must be removed so the HV to the SiBB has to be switched off so that the SiPMs can safely be exposed to the ambient light. Once the test condition has been implemented, e.g. applying glue to the fibre, the lid of the dark box can be replaced and the high voltage restored. Then runs are taken for the final test condition, to be compared with the initial data.

Run lengths are typically 30,000 events with a pulser frequency of 550 Hz, making them approximately one minute in length. The number of events per run was chosen to achieve a good balance between high statistics and the time taken to process the data with recoMore and

Figure 3.1: Fibre testing setup with LED at centre, and SiPMs at each end, of a fibre.

the analysis software detailed in Chapter 2. The number of runs taken is given for each specific test in their relevant sections and was chosen to ensure that sufficient data were obtained while minimising the likelihood of any systematic effects that may arise from the drift of the pulser signal over time. Typically, runs were taken once every five minutes. For other tests, where data was taken in several conditions, consecutive runs were taken to prevent the total duration from getting too long. The number of runs taken also depends on the required precision of the measurement, i.e. more runs for higher statistics.

3.1.1 Selection of Light Intensity

The desired light level was an average of seven photons per event. This level was chosen as it was low enough for individual photoelectrons (PEs) to be resolved by the SiPMs and was also approximately the upper limit for having some events where no light was detected in one or both SiPMs. Having this reference at zero PEs gave the ability to count the number of PEs, which was not essential but provided reassurance when analysing the results. Fig. 3.2 displays an example PE spectrum from a 150,000-event run at the desired light level. The desired light level was achieved by making any necessary adjustments to the pulser voltage, waiting a few minutes for it to stabilise, and taking 8,000-event test runs.

3.2 Selection of the Light Loss Test Parameter

This section details the selection process for the variable used as the test parameter for light losses due to materials in contact with optical fibres. Two parameters were investigated: the light level recorded at each fibre end and the ratio of the light level at each fibre end. Each variable was assessed for its stability over time.

It is important that the natural temporal variation of the system is known so that when the independent variable of the experiment is changed and a light loss is seen, we can be sure to attribute it to the correct cause. Quantifying the variation of the light level without changing

Figure 3.2: Photoelectron spectrum at the desired light level for testing.

any other variables, as far as possible, gives the stability of the system. Any change to the light level smaller than this value is undetectable with this setup, so it sets the limit of the precision of the measurements and therefore determines the minimum light loss we are sensitive to with these tests.

3.2.1 The Mean Signal at Each Fibre End

The first parameter that was investigated was the mean signal produced by the SiPMs at each end of the fibre with a pulsed LED as the light source. The equipment was switched on an hour before taking data so that the system had time to stabilise as far as possible so that any warming-up effects were not present during this test. Once the desired light level was achieved, twenty runs, of 30,000 events each, were taken successively.

The data from each run were split into fifteen 2,000-event slices and the mean signal at each fibre end in each slice was found. Fig. 3.3 is a plot of the mean signal against slice number to visualise the variation over time at each fibre end. At the end of each run, there was a small gap in time ($\approx 5 - 10$ s), which explains the discontinuities in the signal. Grouping the data in 2,000 event slices enabled us to see the time scale of the light variation over time. However, for measurements and stability estimations, the mean signal of the overall runs were used. Fig. 3.4 shows the mean signal at each fibre end per run. It is clear that the light level from the LED pulser is systematically varying, not randomly fluctuating.

The stability, δ_E , of the mean signal, was determined by the ratio of the standard deviation of the run means and the mean of all runs, expressed as a percentage as

$$\delta_E = \frac{\sigma_E}{\mu_E} \times 100\% \quad (3.1)$$

where σ_E and μ_E are the standard deviation, and mean of the mean signals, respectively. The stability of the means at the test and reference ends of the fibre were found to be 8.4% and 8.3% respectively. These values were determined to be too large for the mean to be used as the test parameter for light losses. Therefore, the options were to use a more stable light source or find an alternative test parameter.

It can be seen in Fig. 3.4 that the mean signals per run at each fibre end follow a similar variation over time so as the light level produced by the LED varied over time, both fibre ends

Figure 3.3: Mean signal per 2,000-event slice at each fibre end for twenty runs.

Figure 3.4: Mean signal per run at each fibre end for twenty runs.

experienced the same variation. This meant that the next parameter to investigate was the ratio of the signals at each fibre end, which the data suggest should be more stable.

3.2.2 The Ratio of the Mean Signals at Each Fibre End

For the same data set as in Fig. 3.4, the ratio, R , of the mean signals of each run was calculated by

$$R = \frac{\mu_t}{\mu_r} \quad (3.2)$$

where μ_t and μ_r are the pulse size means at the test and reference ends, respectively. The variation of this ratio over time around the overall mean can be seen in Fig. 3.5. As the ratio appears visually far more stable than the mean signal, further analysis was pursued. The error bar, Δ_R , on each ratio, R , in Fig. 3.5 was calculated by

$$\Delta_R = R \times \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_t}{\mu_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_r}{\mu_r}\right)^2} \quad (3.3)$$

Figure 3.5: Mean ratio per run for a stability test, with line and error band for overall mean.

where the subscripts t and r denote the test and reference ends of the fibre, μ is the mean signal of the run, and σ is the standard error on the mean signal using the slice means. The fibre ends are labelled this way so that one end of the fibre is kept as a constant reference, while the other is modified with the test parameter. Each value of $\sigma_{t(r)}$ is calculated by

$$\sigma_{t(r)} = \frac{\sigma_{t(r),slices}}{\sqrt{N_{slices}}} \quad (3.4)$$

where $\sigma_{t(r),slices}$ is the standard deviation of the 2,000-event slice mean signals at the test(reference) end in the run, and N_{slices} is the number of slices in the run.

The correlation of the mean signals at each fibre end does not need to be considered in the calculation of the run ratio error in Equation. 3.3, as the uncertainties in the mean signals are not correlated variables. The uncertainty comes from statistical fluctuations in each channel. However, it is useful to evaluate the correlation of the mean signals to determine if their ratio is a suitable test parameter. Fig. 3.6 shows a plot of the mean signal at the test end of the fibre versus the mean signal at the reference end for a set of twenty runs, along with the correlation coefficient, ρ , of 0.9996. The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient, ρ , is defined as

$$\rho = \frac{\sum (\mu_t - \bar{\mu}_t) (\mu_r - \bar{\mu}_r)}{\sqrt{\sum (\mu_t - \bar{\mu}_t)^2 \sum (\mu_r - \bar{\mu}_r)^2}} \quad (3.5)$$

where μ is the slice mean and $\bar{\mu}$ is the run mean. This strong correlation justifies the use of their ratio as the test parameter for identifying light loss at one end.

The overall ratio, \bar{R} , of a test is the mean of the ratios of all the runs in the test. The error on this ratio, $\sigma_{\bar{R}}$, is given by

$$\sigma_{\bar{R}} = \frac{\sigma_R}{\sqrt{N_{runs}}} \quad (3.6)$$

where σ_R is the standard deviation of the run ratios, and N_{runs} is the number of runs in the test. \bar{R} and $\sigma_{\bar{R}}$ are displayed as a horizontal line and an error band in Fig. 3.5.

The stability of the ratio over a test, δ_R , was found by

$$\delta_R = \frac{\sigma_R}{\mu_R} \times 100\% \quad (3.7)$$

with σ_R and μ_R being the standard deviation and mean of the ratios of all runs respectively.

Figure 3.6: Correlation between mean signals at each fibre end for twenty runs.

The stability, δ_R , of the ratios was found to be 0.23% over the twenty runs, meaning that in 68% of measurements, we can expect the ratios to agree within $\pm 0.23\%$. This stability addresses the systematic uncertainty introduced by the variation of the ratio of runs taken successively. This means that a 0.69% reduction in the ratio, i.e. a 0.69% light loss, would be a 3σ deviation. Therefore, using the ratio as the dependent variable for the tests, we are sensitive to light losses of 0.69% and higher with confidence that it was caused by the test parameter. This sensitivity is more than acceptable for the purpose of these tests, as light losses of 5 – 10% and higher (depending on the specific application), will be considered a concern at this stage in the LiquidO detector development. Therefore, the ratio of the mean signals at each fibre end per run was used as the test parameter for light losses due to materials in contact with the fibres.

3.3 Fibre Test Designs

This section describes the various fibre test designs that were used to investigate potential light losses along the fibres. These designs build upon the default test setup and method outlined in Section 3.1 and will be referenced in later sections when describing tests that were conducted.

3.3.1 Cell Test

The Cell Test design adds rectangular test cells to the setup described in Section 3.1. The fibre is threaded through these 3D-printed cells that can be filled with the material under test, submerging a 2 cm length of fibre each. A photograph of a fibre with six empty test cells on either side of the LED is shown in Fig. 3.7a. The test procedure for this test is to record the light level at each fibre end from the LED before and after filling one or more of the test cells.

3.3.2 Bead Test

The Bead Test design adds a plastic bead to the test setup described in Section 3.1. The fibre is threaded through these 3D-printed beads and adhered to it using the bonding agent under test. The bonding agent covers 0.5 cm of the fibre when used with these beads, which replicates a typical quantity that will be used for detector assembly. A fibre with a bead on one side of a

mounted LED is shown in Fig. 3.7b. The test procedure for a Bead Test is to record the light level at each fibre end from the LED before and after adhering the bead to the fibre.

(a) Cell Test setup.

(b) Plastic bead thread on a fibre.

Figure 3.7: Cell Test and Bead Test setups for testing adhesives for causing light losses from fibres.

3.3.3 Liquid Immersion Test

The Liquid Immersion Test design adds an open-top aluminium container that can be filled with liquids for the fibre to pass through, to the test setup described in Sec. 3.1. The container can be filled with different quantities of liquid to vary the length of fibre submerged in it. The main purpose of this setup is to investigate the effect on light propagation of the refractive index of the medium surrounding a fibre due to the mechanism described in Section 2.6.2. The container, displayed in Fig. 3.8a is on one side of the LED allowing that side to be used as the test end of the fibre. The procedure with this setup is to record the light level at each fibre end, i.e. take data, either with the container empty, or the fibre outside the container, then take data with the container filled with the material under test and the fibre immersed in it. An aluminium plate can be used as a removable lid to ensure the fibre doesn't accidentally enter the liquid in the container in the initial condition. The overall setup with the lid on the container can be seen in Fig. 3.8b.

(a) Container for submerging fibres in liquid.

(b) Fibre in a Liquid Immersion Test Setup.

Figure 3.8: Setup for investigating the effect of the refractive index of the medium surrounding a fibre.

3.4 Validation Tests

This section details the tests that were conducted to validate the test method and identify any possible confounding variables that may affect the ratio of the light levels at each fibre end. First, the stability of the ratio over a typical experiment procedure was assessed by conducting a simple dry run of a test. The effect of the position of test cells along the fibre, when empty, was investigated by recording the light at each fibre end with the cells at different positions. Most of the real (not validation) tests were conducted with the fibre in air before passing through a glue. However, some tests were conducted with the fibre passing through both air and mineral oil, so another validation test was to investigate the effect of cleaning oil off a fibre. To facilitate comparison of the validation test plots in this section, the y-axis scales for the ratios span a 5% range.

3.4.1 Dry Run Test

The next stage in assessing the test method was to perform dry runs of the experiment, by following the test procedure, detailed in Section 3.1, with the test condition being the simulation of a test. Twenty 30,000-event runs constitute the initial condition data in this dry run test. To simulate the application of a test material, e.g. glue, to the fibre, the lid of the dark box was removed and the fibre was moved around more than it would be in a real test where movement would be minimised as far as possible. This exaggerated movement was to perform the dry run as a worst-case scenario so that if a change in the ratio was observed, another dry run could be performed without this exaggerated movement to see if that was the cause of the change. The lid of the dark box and optical cloth were then replaced, and the power to the SiPMs was restored. Twenty runs were then taken to collect the final condition data.

The data was then analysed as if it were from a real test. The ratio of the mean signals, i.e. the mean light level, at each fibre end before and after opening the box was compared to see if the test procedure had caused a change in the ratio. A plot of the mean ratio per run is shown in Fig. 3.9, with error bands on the overall mean ratio of the initial and final condition data and a vertical line indicating when the lid of the dark box was opened. The fifteenth run in the final condition data set was removed as the ratio from this run was anomalously high.

Figure 3.9: Mean ratio per run for the Dry Run Test with error bands and a vertical line indicating test condition implementation.

Between the initial and final condition data sets, the percentage change in the mean ratio was +0.12%. The stability of the ratio, δ_R , as defined in 3.3 was 0.20% and 0.29% for the

initial and final condition data respectively. Therefore, the change in the ratio between data sets was smaller than the variation within each data set, and so the change was smaller than the sensitivity of the experiment. Furthermore, the initial and final ratios are consistent with each other within 1σ uncertainty as shown by the error bands in Fig. 3.9. Overall the results of this test indicate that the test procedure does not introduce any significant confounding variables that could affect the ratio beyond the inherent stability of the system.

The results of the dry run test validate the proposed setup and method for subsequent testing. The confidence in the setup and method allows for data to be collected that can be analysed to gain insight into the effect of the test materials on the amount of light reaching the end of the fibres.

3.4.2 Cell Position Test

The aim of this test, which utilises the test setup and method outlined in Section 3.3.1, was to evaluate whether changing the positions of the test cells along the fibre affects the ratio of the light level at each fibre end. This was to identify whether the cell's position on the fibre before and after filling it would be a variable that must be carefully controlled. If an effect was found, extra emphasis on keeping the cell position on the fibre constant would be added to the test procedure, to ensure the validity of results using this method. However, the cell positions wouldn't be deliberately moved in any circumstance.

To establish the maximum tolerable variation in cell position that would not affect the test results, two distinct cell configurations were tested, which can be seen in Fig. 3.10. The first configuration had the test cells evenly spaced along the length of fibre on one side of the LED. The second configuration had the test cells positioned close together close to the LED. In each configuration, six 30,000-event runs were taken. This change in cell positions is far greater than would happen when filling the cells for a test.

(a) First cell position configuration.

(b) Second cell position configuration.

Figure 3.10: Cell positions for the validation test.

Fig. 3.11 shows a plot of the ratio at each fibre end per run. The mean ratio had a percentage change of 0.27% between the two configurations, while the stability, δ_R , of the ratio was 0.22% and 0.31% for the first and second configurations respectively. Therefore, there was no observable effect on the ratio when changing the cell position along the fibre. If a significant effect was detected, subsequent tests would have been conducted with smaller and more realistic changes in cell position until an acceptable level of variation was determined.

To conclude, the Cell Position Test demonstrated that changing the positions of the test cells along the fibre does not affect the ratio of the light level at each fibre end. The maximum tolerable variation in cell position was established to be greater than what would occur during

Figure 3.11: Mean ratio per run for the Cell Position Test with error bands and a vertical line indicating movement of cells.

a typical test, and therefore there is no need to carefully control the cell positions in subsequent tests using this method. Additionally, the change in the radius of curvature of the fibre between the two configurations did not have an effect, further validating the test setup and method.

3.4.3 Fibre Cleaning Test with Mineral Oil

The aim of this validation test was to test for any effect on the light level due to cleaning oil off a fibre. This was done using the Liquid Immersion Test design described in Section 3.3.3 and the setup shown in Fig. 3.8. To test the effect of cleaning oil off a fibre, the fibre was initially immersed in mineral oil then it was cleaned and re-immersed in the oil. The cleaning procedure was to wipe the excess oil off the fibre with a clean tissue, then wipe the fibre with an isopropanol-soaked tissue to clean it and finally again with a dry clean tissue. Six 30,000-event runs were taken with the fibre in each of three conditions: immersed in oil, in air after cleaning, and immersed in oil again.

To quantify the effect of cleaning the fibre, the mean ratios of the first and third sets of data with the fibre submerged in oil were compared. Fig. 3.12 shows the mean ratio against the run number for the two sets of data, with error bands on the overall mean ratio of each set. The vertical line indicates when the fibre was cleaned.

The mean ratio changed by 0.20% while the stability, δ_R of the two sets of data was 0.30% and 0.18%. Therefore, this test demonstrates that cleaning mineral oil off a fibre and re-immersing it in the oil does not have a detectable effect on the ratio of the mean signals at each fibre end. This result allowed us to use this setup to conduct a test to investigate both the effect of glue on a fibre passing only through air and the cumulative effect of glue and oil. The effect of the fibre passing through mineral oil compared to air is discussed in Section 5.2.

3.5 Final Test Method and Analysis Process

Using the test setup described in Section 3.1 and the ratio variable detailed in Section 3.2.2, the test method is to implement the test condition, e.g. apply glue to the fibre, on one side of the LED on the fibre only. The mean ratio is compared between data taken before and after the implementation of the test condition to quantify the effect on light propagation. It is important to note that the fibre-to-SiPM coupling was attached to the fibre using an epoxy called 5 Minute

Figure 3.12: Mean ratio per run for the Cleaning Test with error bands and a vertical line indicating fibre cleaning.

Z-POXY. Therefore, the measurements of light loss using this setup are relative to the effect of the fibre coupling, and other factors such as the bend radius of the fibre and external cladding defects. Further information about the equipment, software, and data analysis can be found in Chapter 2. The key stages of the test method and analysis process are as follows:

1. Set up the initial conditions of the fibre in the dark box.
2. Secure the dark box lid and cover it with an optical cloth.
3. Supply power to:
 - Pulser and LED
 - SiBB
 - WaveCatcher
4. Open SiBB and Wavecatcher software and load configurations.
5. Wait at least an hour for pulser stabilisation.
6. Take an 8,000-event test run, process the data using the reconstruction algorithm recoMore, and assess the light level of the pulser using ‘EB_recoMoreScript.py’ (see Section 2.5). Adjust the pulser voltage and repeat as necessary.
7. Take 30,000-event runs to form the initial condition data set.
8. Turn off SiBB HV in the software and check the measured voltage has dropped to a few volts.
9. Remove the optical cloth and dark box lid and implement the test condition to the fibre.
10. Replace the dark box lid and optical cloth then switch on SiBB HV and check the measured voltage is as expected.
11. Wait for the SiBB temperature to stabilise using the SiBB software to monitor it.
12. Take 30,000-event runs to form the final condition data set.
13. Process the data from each run with the reconstruction algorithm, recoMore.
14. Process the recoMore output data to save the pulse sizes to csv files using ‘EB_recoMoreScript.py’.

15. Analyse the data from the .csv files using EB_fibreTestScript.py.
The analysis stages to get the percentage change in the light level are:

- For each run:
 - The ratio of the mean pulse sizes at the test fibre end to the reference fibre end is calculated by Equation 3.2.
 - For each fibre end:
 - * The data is grouped into consecutive 2,000-event slices.
 - * The mean and standard deviation of the pulse sizes in each slice are calculated.
 - The error of the ratio is calculated by Equation 3.3.
- For the initial condition data and the final condition data:
 - The mean of the ratios, and their standard deviation are calculated.
 - The error on the mean of the ratios is calculated by Equation 3.6.
- The percentage change between the initial and final ratios is calculated, which represents the percentage change in the light level at the test end of the fibre.
- The uncertainty on the percentage change in the light level is calculated by adding the initial and final condition ratio errors in quadrature.

Chapter 4

Bondic® Tests

Bondic® is an ultraviolet-curing (UV-curing) adhesive that can bond a wide range of materials in less than five seconds. Its fast curing time makes it a promising candidate for use in LiquidO detectors, particularly for bonding optical fibres under tension. To assess the suitability of Bondic® for this application, tests were conducted to investigate if it caused a loss of light transmission when applied to an optical fibre. Further details can be found at the manufacturer’s website found at this reference: [33].

The first test, detailed in Section 4.1, involved filling all six cells on one side of the LED to maximise the chance of observing a light loss and to achieve a proof of principle for the test method. This was done to demonstrate that the test setup and method could detect a loss of light transmission along one side of a fibre. Subsequent tests, reported in Section 4.2, involved filling one cell, then a second cell, on the other side of the LED to investigate the relationship between the quantity of adhesive used and the size of the resulting light loss. Finally, Section 4.3 reports the test in which a plastic bead was glued to the fibre using Bondic® to determine the effect of the planned amount of glue on light transmission.

Building upon the general test descriptions in Section 3.3.1, this chapter describes the setup and procedure specific to these tests as well as their results, implications and possible explanations based on the properties of Bondic®.

4.1 Proof of Principle Test: Six Cells Filled with Bondic®

In this test, the Cell Test design detailed in Section 3.3.1 was used to assess the effect of Bondic® on light transmission along optical fibres. Data was taken in the initial condition of six cells thread on the fibre on either side of the LED as shown in Fig. 3.7a. To demonstrate proof of principle of the method outlined in Chapter 3, a large quantity of adhesive was applied to the fibre in this first test to maximise the likelihood of causing a light loss. All six cells on one side of the LED were filled with Bondic® and cured using the Bondic® UV LED, and data was again collected to compare the light level at each fibre end before and after applying the adhesive. A schematic diagram of the two test conditions is shown in Fig. 4.1a.

To conduct the test, seven runs of 30,000 events were taken in the first configuration, while fifteen runs of 30,000 events were taken in the second configuration. The six test cells filled with Bondic® after being cured with UV light are shown in Fig. 4.1b.

The plot in Fig. 4.2, clearly shows that the application of Bondic® had a significant effect on the light level from the test side of the fibre, far greater than the stability of the system. The y-axis scale for the ratio spans a range of 20% to facilitate comparison with Fig. 4.5, which has the same range. The percentage light loss caused by applying Bondic® along 12 cm of a fibre was $(16.8 \pm 0.2)\%$. This prompted further investigation into the effect of smaller quantities of Bondic® on light transmission, as detailed in the next two subsections.

(a) Schematic diagram representing the test.

(b) Six test cells filled with cured Bondic®.

Figure 4.1: Bondic® proof of principle test setup.

Figure 4.2: Mean ratio per run for the six-cell Bondic® test, with overall mean error bands and a vertical line indicating Bondic® application.

4.2 One- and Two-Cell Tests with Bondic®

To investigate the effect of smaller quantities of Bondic® on light transmission along an optical fibre, two cells on one side of the LED were filled one at a time. The cell closest to the LED was filled first, followed by the next closest. The fibre used in the previous test with six cells filled was used, so the initial ratio was the final ratio reported in Section 4.1. This means that by causing a light loss to the other side of the fibre the ratio will increase, bringing it closer to the initial value when the fibre was without any Bondic®. Data was taken in each of three conditions:

1. Six cells filled with Bondic® on the reference side of the fibre, and six empty test cells on the test side of the fibre.
2. As in Condition 1 but with one cell filled with Bondic® on the test side of the fibre.
3. As in Condition 1 but with two cells filled with Bondic® on the test side of the fibre.

A schematic diagram of the three test conditions is shown in Fig. 4.3. A run of 33,000 events was taken in each of the three conditions. The ratio of the light level at each fibre end was

Figure 4.3: Schematic diagram representing the three test conditions for the Bondic® one- and two-cell tests.

calculated to compare the light levels in each condition. The resulting light losses from filling one and two cells are presented in Table 4.1. Due to time limitations, it was only possible to conduct a single run in each condition, resulting in a larger uncertainty in the measured light losses compared to other tests.

Table 4.1: Light loss for filling additional cells with Bondic®.

Cells filled		
Initial	Final	Light loss [%]
0	1	14.0 ± 3.9
1	2	3.7 ± 1.0

The results showed that applying Bondic® to a 2 cm section of the optical fibre caused a light loss of $(14.0 \pm 3.9)\%$, while adding an additional 2 cm of Bondic® resulted in only a further $(3.7 \pm 1.0)\%$ light loss. These findings indicate that the light loss caused by Bondic® is not directly proportional to the amount used. Also, the adhesive may affect only some components of light in the fibre (see Section 2.6.2 for the different components of light), leading to a maximum possible loss of light.

4.3 Bead Test with Bondic®

The next stage of testing involved using a realistic amount of Bondic® and quantifying its effect on light transmission. To this aim, the Bead Test procedure described in Section 3.3.2 was followed, which is relevant to the planned application of Bondic® in a prototype LiquidO detector. Due to time constraints, the fibre in the previously reported tests was used but the filled test cells were cut off, leaving 51 cm of fibre to be threaded through a plastic bead, as shown in Fig. 3.7b. The fibre-mounted LED was supported by a metal frame to control the bend radius of the shorter fibre, as shown in Fig. 4.4a.

A 33,000-event run was taken as the initial condition data. The plastic bead was adhered to the fibre, with a length of 0.5 cm of Bondic® and cured with UV light. Fig. 4.4b shows the bead adhered to the fibre with Bondic®, after curing, 10.5 cm from the LED.

Ten 33,000-event runs were taken over a 1.5-hour period as the final condition data for the test. Fig. 4.5 presents a plot of the mean ratio of light levels at each fibre end per run, with a vertical line indicating the time of the Bondic® application. The y-axis scale for the ratio spans a range of 20% to facilitate comparison with Fig. 4.2, which has the same range.

(a) Bondic® Bead Test setup.

(b) Bead adhered to the fibre with Bondic®.

Figure 4.4: Bondic® Bead Test.

Figure 4.5: Mean ratio per run for the Bondic® Bead Test, with overall mean error bands and a vertical line indicating Bondic® application.

The results from this test were that 0.5 cm of Bondic® on a fibre with an LED-to-SiPM distance of 24.5 cm caused a light loss of $(10.7 \pm 0.1)\%$. This suggests that the planned quantity of Bondic® does not result in the maximum amount of light loss observed with larger quantities. Additionally, it is possible that the effect of 0.5 cm of Bondic® on the same length of fibre used in previous tests could be less than 10% once light loss due to attenuation is accounted for (see Section 2.6.4 for information about fibre attenuation lengths).

4.4 Bondic® Discussion

The main finding of this section’s work is that the application of Bondic® to a length of fibre with an SiPM greater than 24.5 cm from the light source will result in a maximum light loss of $(10.7 \pm 0.1)\%$. Recall that this light loss is in addition to that caused by the fibre-to-SiPM coupling, which cannot be measured with this setup. This result indicates that Bondic® remains a viable adhesive for use in LiquidO detector applications, with the expected light loss likely to be even lower when used with longer fibres due to attenuation effects (see Section 2.6.4). Furthermore, the successful development and application of the test method provide a valuable tool for

future investigations into the effect of materials on light transmission in optical fibres. This will enable improvements in the design of LiquidO detectors to maximise their light yield and provide information which can be added to the detector simulations to improve their accuracy. Further work was needed to understand the mechanism of the light loss caused by Bondic®. Chapter 5 investigates one such possible mechanism, by studying the effect of the index of refraction of the medium surrounding the external cladding of the fibre (see Section 2.6.2).

Chapter 5

Refractive Index Investigations

The work in this chapter aimed to investigate the impact of the refractive index of materials in contact with optical fibres on light propagation. Specifically, the focus was on determining to what extent the refractive index of Bondic® adhesive contributed to the light loss results detailed in Chapter 4.

The hypothesis is that the higher refractive index of the adhesive compared to the external cladding causes the external cladding component of the light in the fibre to bend out into the material, leading to a detected light loss (see Sections 2.6.2 and 2.6.3). The plan with this section of work was to find out if this explanation accounts for the entire light loss that was reported in Chapter 4.

There are other factors with Bondic® which may have contributed to the light loss such as UV absorbance, chemical compatibility with the cladding, and the intense UV light used to cure the adhesive. Therefore, it was important to isolate the variables to draw conclusions and generalise the results to other materials for use in the wider LiquidO detector development program.

The refractive index of the material surrounding the fibre was the first variable investigated, for several reasons. Firstly, in a LiquidO detector, light propagates along a fibre immersed in an opaque scintillator with a higher refractive index than that of the external cladding, making the applicability of this work more relevant than the previous tests. Secondly, the external cladding has a shorter attenuation length than the other layers of the fibre (see Section 2.6.4). For these reasons, it's unlikely to collect this light from a large LiquidO detector, and therefore, its loss is not a significant concern. Having an easy-to-use, quick-curing adhesive may be of higher priority than preserving the external cladding light. Thirdly, understanding the light loss due to this mechanism will be applicable to all future tests and results.

To determine the refractive index effect, tests were conducted to measure light loss when optical fibres were in contact with materials of known refractive indices that were also known not to damage the fibres. The materials used were ultrapure water (UPW) and mineral oil (see Section 5.1 and 5.2 respectively). These tests provide insights into the impact of the refractive index of the surrounding material on light propagation, aiding in the development of a better understanding of the performance of optical fibres in opaque scintillator detectors.

5.1 Water Immersion Test

When a fibre has an external cladding with a refractive index higher than that of the medium it's in, external cladding light is able to propagate along the fibre through total internal reflection at the cladding-air boundary (see Section 2.6.2). To investigate this, the Liquid Immersion Test setup described in Section 3.3.3 was used with UPW as the liquid. UPW has a refractive index of 1.33 [34] and the external cladding of the fibre is fluor-acrylic with a refractive index of 1.42. Referring to the simulation results shown in Fig. 2.16, a lower trapping efficiency of external

cladding light than in air is predicted, and so a light loss is expected with this test. Three 30,000-event runs were taken before and after filling the container with UPW which immersed a length of 11 ± 2 cm of the fibre. The fibre in the empty container and the container filled with UPW can be seen in Fig. 5.1.

(a) Fibre passing through the empty container between the LED and SiPM.

(b) Fibre passing through UPW in the container between the LED and SiPM.

Figure 5.1: Immersion test setup with empty and full containers

Fig. 5.2 shows a plot of the ratio of the mean light level at each fibre end per run. The y-axis scale for the ratio spans a range of 10% to facilitate comparison with Fig. 5.4, which has the same range. The change in the ratio between the two sets of data was $(0.2 \pm 0.3) \%$, which falls within the variation of the system found in the stability test in Section 3.2.2. Furthermore, the uncertainty of this measurement is larger than the change in the light level. Therefore, immersing the fibre in UPW had no detectable effect on the light level.

Figure 5.2: A plot of the ratio of the mean light level at each fibre end per run with error bands around the overall means of each data set and a vertical line indicating when the fibre was immersed in UPW.

5.1.1 Discussion of the Water Immersion Test

This test found no light loss, however, the simulation results shown in Fig. 2.16 suggest that a reduction in the trapping efficiency of the external cladding component of light would result in a light loss, which was not observed in this test. The lack of detectable effect from immersing the fibre in UPW could be explained by a filtering effect. Once light is lost from the fibre due to a specific mechanism, applying the same mechanism again cannot cause any additional light loss. Therefore, it is possible that the initial conditions of this test already removed the light that would be lost by immersing the fibre in UPW, which would explain no further light loss was observed in this test. It could be that the light lost due to the fibre-to-SiPM coupling using epoxy and other attenuation effects may have already filtered out the light that could have been lost due to immersing the fibre in UPW. To better understand the results, the accuracy of the simulation could also be improved to test and, if it's correct, demonstrate this explanation. This would involve adding features such as fibre bend radius, attenuation lengths, and surface defects and impurities to the simulation. If after adding these factors to the simulation, a light loss due to immersing the fibre in water is still expected, this would further suggest that the fibre coupling is causing the discrepancy.

If the results had indicated a light loss, the length of fibre immersed in the UPW would have been measured more precisely, and a repeat of the test with more runs would have been conducted for improved statistics. However, this was not deemed necessary due to the absence of detectable light loss.

5.2 Oil Immersion Test

This test investigates a scenario where a fibre is immersed in a material with a higher refractive index than its external cladding. In such cases, when light in the external cladding reaches the cladding-medium boundary, it bends away from the fibre, causing the light to leave the fibre (see Section 2.6.2). The aim of this test is to induce this phenomenon and quantify the resulting light loss.

The test design in Section 3.3.3 was used with mineral oil in the container. Mineral oil was chosen for its refractive index, which falls between 1.47 and 1.48 [35], higher than that of the external cladding of the fibre (1.42 [24]). Additionally, the refractive index of the transparent organic scintillator, LAB, in NoWaSH is 1.48 [9] and so we know that the refractive index of the scintillator in a LiquidO detector will be higher than the cladding. By immersing 20 ± 2 cm of the fibre in mineral oil, as shown in Fig. 5.3, a light loss should occur due to a reduction in the trapping efficiency of the external cladding light, as demonstrated by the simulation results shown in Fig. 2.16.

Twenty 30,000-event runs were taken before and after immersing the fibre in mineral oil. Fig. 5.4 shows a plot of the ratio of the mean light level at each fibre end per run, displaying the light loss induced by the oil immersion. The y-axis scale for the ratio spans a range of 10% to facilitate comparison with Fig. 5.2, which has the same range. The change in the ratio between the two sets of data was $4.7 \pm 0.1\%$, which corresponds to the resultant light loss.

5.2.1 Discussion of the Oil Immersion Test

Optical fibres are a vital component of LiquidO detectors (see Section 1.2) as they enable the extraction of light from the scintillator, carrying information about the energy deposition and position of the particle interactions. Understanding how light behaves in these fibres is important for optimisation during the detector development and for the accuracy of the detector simulations. One aspect of this is how light can be lost from the fibres after it has been trapped, and a key part is that external cladding light can be lost due to it refracting away from the

Figure 5.3: Fibre immersed in mineral oil on one side of the LED. For scale, the bolt holes are on a 25-mm pitch.

fibre rather than totally internally reflecting. This is what these tests have been investigating to develop our understanding of fibres.

Tests were performed by immersing the fibre in liquids with both lower and higher refractive indices than its external cladding (Sections 5.1 and 5.2 respectively). Light loss was observed when the fibre was immersed in a medium with a refractive index higher than that of its external cladding, but not with a lower refractive index. This suggests that this setup is sensitive to light losses caused by immersing the fibre in a medium with a refractive index 1.42 but not with a refractive index of 1.33. This is likely due to the baseline light losses from the fibre induced by the use of epoxy in the fibre-to-SiPM coupling.

Based on these oil test results, it could be concluded that the external cladding light contributed $4.7 \pm 0.1\%$ of the total light collected at the ends of the fibre. However, this value is only applicable to the specific test conditions and cannot be generalised beyond this test, including to other tests using the same setup or other fibres of the same type due to the numerous variables that affect the amount of external cladding light (see Section 2.6.4). To improve the applicability to realistic detector scenarios, the light loss from oil at different light intensities could be investigated, as the light intensity in a detector varies with the energy deposited by the incident particle. However, this was not studied here due to limitations imposed by the LED pulser's time to stabilise at a particular intensity.

Of particular importance is the dependence of the proportion of the total light that is external cladding light on the distance between the light source and the light detector. This is because the external cladding light has a shorter attenuation length compared to the other components of light in the fibre (see Section 2.6.4). As a result, the proportion of external cladding light lost from the fibre increases with distance from the source, even if the refractive index of the surrounding medium is lower than that of the external cladding. It is important to note that the attenuation length of external cladding light can vary significantly between individual pieces of fibre and can be affected by various factors, such as damage, dirt, and dust, that are difficult to control. Manufacturers face challenges in producing defect-free external cladding layers, which can be visible under a microscope. For example, defects can be seen in Fig. 5.5 which is a microscope image produced after the fibre was cleaned with Micro A07 Citric Acid Cleaner.

To improve the reproducibility and generalisability of the previous tests, it would have been advantageous to more precisely control the distance between the LED and the fibre end being tested. Initially, the tests were designed with the flexibility to adjust the LED position. However,

Figure 5.4: Ratio of the mean light level at each fibre end per run with a vertical line indicating immersion of fibre in mineral oil.

Figure 5.5: Microscope images of a section of fibre showing surface defects.

in hindsight, fixing the LED at a consistent position for each fibre may have been more beneficial. In the previously reported tests, the LED position was controlled in that care was taken not to move it during a test. However, the position was only approximately at the centre of the fibre and so was not controlled between fibres and between tests. The attenuation length of the external cladding light is short (see Section 2.6.4), meaning that small changes in the LED position have a detectable impact on the amount of external cladding light present in these test setups. As the importance of this variable became apparent, care was taken to precisely position the LED in the same way for the final tests of this project, although there is still the possibility that the LED was inadvertently moved while setting up the tests. Therefore, to improve the reproducibility and generalisability of the results, future modifications to the test design could involve fixing the LED on the fibre.

As for the applicability of these results to the LiquidO detector development, it should be noted that in a detector, the source-to-detection distances vary greatly. It is therefore possible that some external cladding light will be detected, particularly when the light is produced near the edges of the detector or in a small prototype. Such edge effects with particle detectors are common, and a more comprehensive understanding of the external cladding light could be valuable in improving the accuracy of detector simulations. Therefore, it is likely that further research in this area will continue beyond the scope of this project, particularly in developing the detector simulations by incorporating the various factors that impact the propagation of light along fibres.

As more was learned about the factors affecting the external cladding light, the testing procedures were revised. This included cleaning the fibres with isopropanol just before testing. Additionally, gloves were introduced when handling the fibres to minimise the risk of contamination. In earlier work, the fibres were only cleaned after they were assembled for use in testing but were handled carefully to avoid damage.

In conclusion, this investigation has demonstrated the loss of light from optical fibres when immersed in materials with a higher refractive index than their external cladding. The study has also highlighted important factors that affect the external cladding component of light, providing prospects for future research and test design development.

5.2.2 Discussion of the Oil Immersion Test and Bondic® Tests

The refractive index investigation of this chapter aimed to isolate and quantify the light loss caused by surrounding a fibre with a material of refractive index higher than that of its external cladding. The oil immersion test revealed that for a light source to fibre end distance of approximately 60 cm, this light loss was $4.7 \pm 0.1\%$. This gave an estimation for the proportion of external cladding light in the fibre. For the Bondic® tests, detailed in Chapter 4, the light losses were at least twice as much as this. Therefore, from this refractive index investigation, it can be concluded that Bondic® causes more than the external cladding light to be lost from the fibre. This means that other mechanisms of light loss are likely involved with this adhesive. Potential candidates, as mentioned in the introduction of Chapter 5, are UV absorbance, damage to the external cladding, and possibly the inner cladding too. The results suggest that Bondic® is not a suitable adhesive for future larger prototypes and detectors as it causes loss of the inner cladding light and possibly the core light too. The trapping efficiency, as detailed in Section 2.6.3, of optical fibres is very low and is, therefore, a huge source of light loss between the scintillator and light collectors. This means that once the light has been trapped by the fibre it is of great importance to minimise any losses of this light, to maximise the light yield from the detector. However, for the next prototype detector that is currently being built, a $\leq 10\%$ light loss is an acceptable loss given the importance of having an immediately available quick-curing adhesive that we know can hold the fibres under tension. Future work can focus on finding alternative adhesives with a lower light loss for larger detectors where a 10% light loss may not be acceptable.

It is suspected that Bondic® is causing some damage to the cladding(s) of the fibre. Further work could focus on deepening this understanding, however, for the purposes of this project, the focus was shifted to testing another quick-curing epoxy called 5 Minute Z-POXY (hereafter referred to as Z-POXY). This was decided because the Bondic® results were showing surprisingly high so I thought it was important to check that Z-POXY wasn't causing such high light losses as it is currently used in LiquidO detectors to attach the SiPM connectors to the fibres. In particular, the aim was to determine if this epoxy caused any light loss in addition to oil. The strategy for this next stage of testing was to first quantify the light loss from applying Z-POXY to the fibre surrounded by air and then see if it caused any additional light loss after being immersed in oil. The details of this testing are presented in Chapter 6.

Chapter 6

Z-POXY Tests

5 Minute Z-POXY (hereafter referred to as Z-POXY) made by ZAP is a two-part epoxy adhesive that dries clear and has a five-minute curing time, making it a useful adhesive for building LiquidO detector prototypes. It has been used to adhere SiPM connectors to optical fibres. As demonstrated in Chapter 4, the application of adhesives to optical fibres can cause light to be lost, reducing the light yield from the detector. In this investigation, tests were conducted to quantify the light loss caused by Z-POXY when applied to optical fibres both in air and after immersion in oil, which has a refractive index higher than that of the fibre's external cladding. The aim of these tests was to quantify the light loss caused by Z-POXY and, in particular, to determine whether Z-POXY causes any additional light loss than that from oil.

6.1 Z-POXY Cell Test

To compare the performance of Z-POXY with Bondic®, the test with one cell detailed in Section 4.2 was replicated using the test design described in Section 3.3.1, filling a test cell 2 cm from the LED with Z-POXY. Runs of 30,000 events were taken; fourteen runs as the initial condition data set and nineteen after filling the cell with Z-POXY. The test setup with the empty cell and filled cell is shown in Fig. 6.1. Note that the cured Z-POXY was full of bubbles and did not look clear; this is not how the epoxy usually cures but this occurred due to filling a cell as opposed to spreading a smaller quantity onto the fibre.

Six empty test cells were threaded on either side of an LED mounted on the fibre. Each fibre end was connected to an SiPM for recording the light.

(a) Empty test cells thread on a fibre.

(b) Cell filled with cured Z-POXY.

Figure 6.1: Z-POXY Cell Test setup

A plot of the ratio of the mean energies at each fibre end per run is shown in Fig. 6.2, with a vertical line indicating when the cell was filled with Z-POXY. The drop in the ratio demonstrates that a loss of light was caused by the application of Z-POXY to the fibre, this light loss was $1.7 \pm 0.1\%$. As previously reported in Section 4.2, a similar test with Bondic® resulted in a light loss more than ten times greater than with Z-POXY.

Figure 6.2: A plot of mean ratio of the light level at each fibre end against run number. A vertical line indicates when the Z-POXY adhesive was applied to the fibre.

6.2 Z-POXY Bead and Oil Test

The test detailed in Section 6.1 showed that the use of Z-POXY does not cause a large amount of light to be lost from the fibre. This section investigates a realistic quantity of Z-POXY at a greater distance from the LED, and whether the light loss still occurs when the fibre is surrounded by a material of higher refractive index than its external cladding, as in a LiquidO detector. To this aim, the Bead Test and the Liquid Immersion Test, as described in Section 3.3.2 and Section 3.3.3, were combined. This test also allowed for some comparison with the Bondic® test reported in Section 4.3. However, note that the length of fibre used for the Bondic® tests was shorter than for this test with Z-POXY (51 cm and 130 cm respectively). Data was taken in each of the following conditions:

1. Fibre in air and thread through a bead Fig. 6.3a.
2. Fibre in oil and thread through a bead Fig. 6.3b.
3. Fibre in oil with the bead glued on Fig. 6.3c.
4. Fibre in air with the bead glued on Fig. 6.3d.

This enabled the effect of 0.5 cm of Z-POXY both in air and in oil to be investigated. Fig. 6.3 shows the test setup in each condition. Each run consisted of 30,000 events, with twenty runs in conditions 1-3 and thirty in condition 4. The data in conditions 1 and 2 are from the oil test discussed in Section 5.2. Between condition 3 and 4, the fibre was cleaned as per the procedure detailed in the Fibre Cleaning Test in Section 3.4.3, in which cleaning the fibre was demonstrated to have no detectable effect on the light level. Due to this validation test, we were able to conduct this test with confidence in the measurements.

Figure 6.3: Z-POXY and Oil Test setup.

Figure 6.4: Mean ratio of the light level at each fibre end per run, with vertical lines indicating fibre immersion in oil, Z-POXY application, and fibre cleaning.

Fig. 6.4 shows a plot of the ratio of mean energies at each fibre end per run for this test, with vertical lines indicating where each test condition was implemented. The y-axis scale for the ratio spans a 10% range to facilitate comparison with other plots. Table. 6.1 summarises

Table 6.1: Light loss for oil and Z-POXY tests.

Test condition		Light loss [%]
Initial	Final	
Air	Oil	4.7 ± 0.1
Oil	Oil + Z-POXY	0.0 ± 0.1
Air	Air + Z-POXY	1.7 ± 0.1

the percentage change in light levels between test conditions. The light loss due to Z-POXY on a fibre in air was $(1.7 \pm 0.1)\%$. Comparing this result with the Bondic® test reported in Section 4.3, the use of Z-POXY caused a light loss more than ten times smaller than Bondic®—a relation also found in Section 6.1. The light loss caused by Z-POXY in addition to the oil was below the sensitivity of the experiment, indicating that the use of this epoxy in LiquidO detectors is not a cause for concern.

6.3 Z-POXY Tests Discussion

It is important to restate that Z-POXY is used to adhere the FC connectors that couple the fibre ends to the SiCs. This means that the measurements of the effect of Z-POXY on light transmission are relative to the light already lost by applying the epoxy to the fibre. With this test setup, it's not possible to measure the total light loss because the FC connectors require the use of an adhesive. The results of this test show that the application of 0.5 cm of Z-POXY does not cause any additional effect than the light already lost by immersing the fibre in oil and adhering the FC connectors to the fibre (also with Z-POXY). A future test could be to adhere the FC connectors with a different epoxy and repeat the Z-POXY test to compare outcomes. However, this is unlikely to be pursued due to the benefits of Z-POXY such as its quick-cure time, lack of heat production when curing, and the results of this test.

Drawing upon the investigation in Chapter 5, we conclude that Z-POXY affects only the external cladding light and its mechanism of light loss is the bending of light out of the fibre at the external cladding to the surrounding medium boundary. This is supported by the reduction in trapping efficiency of the external cladding light shown by the simulation results in Fig. 2.16. The Z-POXY results, Chapter 5 results, and the trapping efficiency simulation suggest that the refractive index of Z-POXY is between that of UPW and mineral oil as the light loss was greater than in water but smaller than in oil. Although it should be noted that the quantity of Z-POXY was small compared to the quantity of oil, so this may be a factor in the results. The results with Z-POXY make it an ideal adhesive for use in LiquidO detectors, where it is unlikely that external cladding light will be collected and so it would not lower the light yield of the detector. However, the cure time of five minutes does not lend Z-POXY to applications that require the fibres to be held under tension while it is curing and so it is not a candidate to replace Bondic® (see Chapter 4). This is an issue that is difficult to resolve as epoxies with faster curing times tend to produce heat that can damage the fibre.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

The relevant sections of this report include a discussion and conclusion of individual tests, while an overall conclusion, future outlook, and reflection are presented in this chapter.

7.1 Overall conclusion

The findings of this project suggest that in a large-scale LiquidO detector, it is unlikely that the external cladding component of the light in the fibres will be collected. This is due to the immersion of the fibres in a medium with a higher refractive index than that of their cladding. Therefore, provided the chosen adhesives do not damage the cladding, any light loss they cause on a short fibre in air is not a significant concern for the detector's overall light yield. This project has contributed to the LiquidO research group's understanding of light propagation along optical fibres, and has highlighted areas that require further study in future work. For example, more accurate fibre simulations are required to fully understand the experimental results of this project and to accurately simulate LiquidO detectors in general. This project demonstrates the importance of consideration and testing of all components in the design and construction of detectors to ensure optimal performance, particularly for maximising the light yield.

7.2 Future Outlook

Given the opportunity to continue the work started with this project, further investigation could be done in several areas. Firstly, to understand the light loss caused by Bondic®, further testing could be done to determine if it should be rejected for use in a large-scale LiquidO detector. A test similar to that in Section 6.2 could be conducted with Bondic® to determine the light loss caused by this adhesive in addition to the loss in oil. An additional test could involve applying the UV light used to cure Bondic®, without applying the adhesive, to determine whether the UV light damages the fibre or if any damage is due to the bonding agent itself. Further investigation could also be done by examining a fibre with Bondic® applied under a microscope. This would reveal if the external cladding is damaged by Bondic®, as expected, and whether the inner cladding is also affected. The implications of cladding damage are also relevant to LiquidO detectors that will use Kuraray B-3 fibres, as it is likely that the external cladding is a similar material as the Saint-Gobain fibres (they are described by slightly different names by the manufacturers). Future fibre testing may be conducted with Kuraray B3 fibres to ensure their suitability for use in LiquidO detectors. The test method and analysis software developed in this project can be applied to future testing, making implementing the process faster.

A potentially interesting avenue for further investigation is to conduct tests with oil and adhesive at varying light intensities. The aim of this test would be to determine if there is a

correlation between the light loss caused by an adhesive and the light source intensity, or whether the percentage light loss remains constant regardless of the intensity. Such a test would be more representative of a LiquidO detector, where the scintillation light varies based on the energy of the incident particle, improving the overall applicability of the results. Due to the instability of the pulser and the considerable time taken to achieve the desired light level, I decided not to pursue this investigation. In general, future investigations into light losses along optical fibres would benefit from a more stable light source to make testing more time efficient. To improve the applicability of the test results to a LiquidO detector, the setup could be modified to immerse the light source in the oil to replicate scintillation light at a known intensity. Furthermore, large-scale LiquidO detectors will have greater distances from light production to collection than the typical 60 – 70 cm distances used in this project. This distance was limited by the size of the dark box used, but the fibre could be coiled to use longer fibres with the same setup. However, the effect of coiling the fibre would need to be considered and it would not be representative of a LiquidO detector. Alternatively, the setup could be modified to have the SiPMs opposite each other so the fibre could be straight while under test. Another test could investigate the effect of surface impurities, such as dust and fingerprints on the external cladding of the fibres, on light transmission to see if its significant enough to be detected with the test setup. This data could provide insight into the variation of results obtained with different fibres.

Another area for future work is to complete the measurement of the attenuation length of the fibre in the test setup. In this project, data was taken with the LED at several positions along the fibre, and analysis was started. The attenuation length is typically modeled as a double exponential, consisting of a short and a long component, but I was not able to fit the model to the data successfully in the time available. Future work could work on the analysis and/or take more data to improve the statistics. Completing this measurement could provide additional insight into the results of this project and help explain the discrepancy between the expected reduction in trapping efficiency (Section 2.6.3) and the results of the UPW test (Section 5.1). The attenuation length of the fibre could also be added to the fibre simulations to improve their accuracy. In general, further work is needed to improve the simulation of light propagation in WLS fibres for use in LiquidO detectors. For example, the simulation results presented in Fig. 2.16 modelled a straight fibre, while the fibres used in the test setup were curved to reach SiPMs in the same plane.

7.3 Reflection

Early in this project, I focused on characterising the new LED pulser and SiPMs and validating the test method under development. In hindsight, it may have been beneficial to invest more time in a literature review on light propagation in WLS fibres as I learnt a lot of theory in the later part of the project. However, I focused on the experimental aspects such as data taking and analysis, while other members of the LiquidO research group spent time on the theory and simulation aspects. Our combined efforts led to the research group having an improved understanding of light propagation and sources of light losses in WLS fibres, as well as the development of a reliable test method that produced meaningful results.

In addition, my early work with the SiPMs led to an unexpected discovery. While characterising the new LED pulser, I noticed poor resolution from one of the SiPMs compared to the expected SiPM performance. I conducted several tests to isolate the cause of this behaviour, ruling out other components of the setup, to show that it was the SiPM. This SiPM was investigated by a member of the LiquidO collaboration who identified that it has a different quenching resistor, which made the quenching time slower and resulted in a different signal pulse shape. This meant that the waveform template used in the reconstruction algorithm, recoMore, was not appropriate for the SiPM’s signal, leading to poor results. This finding has been shared with the LiquidO research group to serve as a diagnostic checklist item if future SiPM issues arise.

Through this project, I have improved my experimental skills, in particular Python programming and data analysis, as well as learnt the theory of WLS fibres through presentations in LiquidO meetings and my own reading. Furthermore, I regularly presented my work to the Sussex LiquidO group as well as at the international LiquidO collaboration meetings. Over the course of this project, my presentation skills have significantly improved. By aiming to regularly present my work, this ensured I continuously reviewed the test and analysis methodology which improved the quality of the work over the duration of the project. This meant that I obtained results from a range of tests which addressed the objectives of the project, and could spend time at the end of the project fine-tuning the analysis, with a particular focus on ensuring the errors associated with the measurements were well-estimated.

If I were to start this project again, I would have invested the time to automate my code and modularise it into functions sooner than I did. This took less time to implement than I anticipated, with the benefit of significantly reducing the data processing time. The experience I gained from developing my own data analysis code will be useful in future projects, and the test and analysis methods and code themselves can be used and adapted for future research in this area. In the future, if I have any ideas to improve the time efficiency of data processing, I will implement them as soon as possible.

My logbook-keeping skills improved over the duration of this project. To me, it is always worth spending some extra time on good record-keeping as it pays off in the long run. I would particularly recommend including a concise summary at the top of each daily page, as well as a summary page with a one-line overview of each day's work. Taking some time to do this at the end of each week is beneficial as it makes finding things in the future much faster, and reflecting on the week helps to keep track of progress and ensures that planned tasks or ideas don't get forgotten. I have found that keeping a dedicated 'to-do list' page in the logbook is useful for storing tasks in one location, rather than having them scattered throughout various pages. It's also helpful to make a more detailed to-do list in the day's logbook page before starting work to ensure the essential tasks get done, and that work is well-planned and focused. In hindsight, it would have been better to upload photographs taken in the lab to the corresponding day's data folder, rather than solely to the logbook, as the images' resolution was significantly reduced. This made them unsuitable for inclusion in my report, resulting in unnecessary time spent searching for the original images.

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